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SANSA Newsletter 45

SANSA NEWSLETTER

WHY A NATIONAL SPIDER SPECIES CHECKLIST?

Any biodiversity project in a country is dependent on correct and regularly updated national species lists. To obtain such a list, all the known species data from published taxonomic and faunistic papers and primary data from specimens in national collections need to be collated into a database. This was done with the SANSA database for spiders and enabled us to publish the first species list for spiders in 2010.

This data formed the basis of the First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). The Atlas (1160 pp.) provided information on 2003 species. This document is available from the Agricultural Research Council website but can now also be downloaded from Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7628809>.

The original descriptions of the majority of species described between the late 1980s and early 1990s are very basic, lacking detailed morphological data, drawings, detailed collecting data, and their natural history remains mainly unknown. It is therefore important to systematically uncover their taxonomic validity, provide data to be able to recognise them and to document their biology, and interpret their evolutionary histories. Before this could be done it is important to at least have a checklist available of species known from a country.

However, due to the large number of taxonomic changes and the large number of new species that have been described, a new updated national lists will be available soon.

REFERENCE

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N., & JOCQUÉ R. 2010. First Atlas of the Spiders of South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). South African National Survey of Arachnida Technical Report 2010, version 1, 1160 pp. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7628809>

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EDITORIAL COMMITTEE

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman
dippenaaransie@gmail.com

Rudi Steenkamp
rudolphsteinkampf@gmail.com

Ruan Booysen
booyesenr@ufs.ac.za

Stefan Foord
stefan@foord.co

<https://zenodo.org/communities/sansa/>

The new spider field guide will be on the shelf: August 2023

Thoroughly revised and updated, this long-awaited new edition of *Field Guide to the Spiders of South Africa* remains the most comprehensive guide to South African spiders published to date. It features over 780 of the more common spider species encountered in the field and in homes and gardens, as well as representative species from some of the rarer spider families.

Key features

- * 'Quick Keys' to the 72 South Africa spider families provide a useful starting point to identification.
- * Succinct species and genus accounts cover identifying characteristics, breeding, behaviour, distribution and conservation status.
- * Clear colour photographs and/or illustrations support each entry.
- * Introductory chapter discusses spider morphology, spider life cycle, the functions of silk, as well as spider collection techniques.
- * Section on venom identifies species that pose a danger to humans, unpacks neurotoxic and cytotoxic venom, and details the symptoms and treatment of spider bites.

SMALLEST SALTICIDAE IN AFRICA: A SOUTH AFRICAN ENDEMIC

Members of the salticid genus *Tanzania* are known for their very small size. The genus was originally named *Lilliput*, but the name was preoccupied and replaced with *Tanzania* (Koçak & Kemal, 2008). Seven species are known, with five species recorded from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2023). Only one species, *Tanzania yellapragadai* Prajapati & Dudhatra, 2022, is known from India and at only 1.29 mm, is the smallest salticid in the genus and one of the smallest in the world.

Recently, Ludwig Eksteen collected a small spider in Tzaneen that was sent to Charles Haddad for identification. Charles confirmed that it was a new, undescribed *Tanzania* sp. with a body length of only 1.35 mm. Intrigued by the size of this spider, macro photographer and salticid enthusiast, Vida van der Walt, corresponded with several salticid experts, and it turned out that this is the smallest salticid species yet to be collected in Africa. It was also suggested that this species, with its small size and bright orange colour, could be a mite mimic. Members of *Tanzania* are probably more widely distributed, but due to their tiny size and colouration, they could be overlooked in collected materials or treated as undeterminable immature specimens.

REFERENCE

KOÇAK A.Ö. & KEMAL M. 2008. New synonyms and replacement names in the genus group taxa of Araneida. *Centre for Entomological Studies Ankara, Miscellaneous Papers* 139-140: 1–4.

WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2023. World Spider Catalog. Version 24. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>.

Tanzania sp. male from Tzaneen. Photo credits: Vida vd Walt.

NEW WADICOSA (LYCOSIDAE) COMBINATION

KRONESTEDT T. 2023. Species of *Wadicosa* (Araneae, Lycosidae): transfer of four species from Africa currently placed in *Pardosa*. *Zootaxa* 5227(5): 531–548.

Abstract

Pardosa enucleata Roewer, 1959, *P. mabweana* Roewer, 1959, *P. manubriata* Simon, 1898, and *P. sordidecolorata* (Strand, 1906) are redescribed and illustrated. The male of *P. enucleata* (erroneously described previously as *P. manubriata*) and that of *P. mabweana* are described here for the first time. Arguments are provided for transferring these four species to *Wadicosa* Zyuzin, 1985. *W. enucleata* comb. nov., *W. mabweana* comb. nov., and *W. manubriata* comb. nov. constitute a monophyletic group which shares a unique configuration of the embolus in the males as well as paired structures of a specific texture associated with the spermathecae in the females. *W. enucleata* and *W. manubriata* both have a wide distribution in Southern Africa, the northern most record of the former being in Ivory Coast, Togo, and the Central African Republic, and that of *W. manubriata* in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC). *W. mabweana* was originally described on material from the DRC and is here reported also from Angola, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, and Namibia. *W. sordidecolorata* comb. nov. was originally described from Ethiopia, and is here reported also from Uganda, Cameroon, and Ivory Coast. *Pardosa darolii* (Strand, 1906) syn. nov. is recognised as a junior synonym to *W. sordidecolorata*.

Wadicosa sp. Photo credits: Peter Webb

★ *Wadicosa enucleata* ○ *W. manubriata*

FIGURE 1. Collection localities for the two *Wadicosa* spp. in Southern Africa.

Wadicosa enucleata

Distribution: *Eastern Cape:* Grahamstown, Dunbrody, Van Stadens River, Margate. *Limpopo:* Blouberg, Musina. *Mpumalanga:* Piet Retief.

Wadicosa manubriata

Distribution: *Eastern Cape:* Dunbrody, Graaff-Reinet. *KwaZulu-Natal:* Lady-smith, near Mzimba-Hill. *Limpopo:* Dendron, farm Vergeval. *Mpumalanga:* Lower Sabie River, Kruger National Park. *Northern Cape:* Blaauwkrantz, south of Calvinia, Garies. *Western Cape:* Laingsburg, Paarl, Elands Bay.

EKAPA NEW ENTYPESIDAE GENUS

RÍOS-TAMAYO D., LYLE R. & SOLE C.L. 2023. *Ekapa*, a new genus of mygalomorph spiders (Araneae, Entypesidae) from South Africa. *African Invertebrates* 64(1): 1–12.

Abstract

A new genus of mygalomorph spider, *Ekapa* gen. nov., is described from South Africa. The new genus was formed to include the species *Hermacha curvipes* Purcell, 1902 and *Hermacha nigra* Tucker, 1917. These species are synonymised based on their somatic similarities, such as fovea shape, cheliceral teeth distribution, ocular pattern, presence of preening combs, and their close geographic distribution. The new genus proposed is distinguished by the presence of a projection in the retroventral side of the palpal tibia in males, together with a distinctive copulatory bulb shape; and in females by the shape of their spermathecae, with a high base and apical stalks that open into oval apical receptacles.

Ekapa curvipes

Distribution: *Western Cape:* Simonstown, Bergvliet Flats, Cape Peninsula: Cape Town, Constantia, Table Mountain National Park.

PROJECTS IN PROGRESS

Pitfall trapping in the Waterberg massif

A brief exploration of spider records in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) in the Waterberg region reveals that there are very few records and that surveys were limited to the lower elevations (Fig. 1). A recent PhD by Gregory Channing from Tshwane University of Technology explored the impact of fire on spider diversity in Welgevonden Game Reserve and included some intensive sampling. Unfortunately, specimens from this study were not deposited in a recognised collection.

If we exclude the NCA records that are not nearby or on the massif (Fig. 1), we remain with around 1000 identified specimens. The bulk (55%) was collected on the Springbokvlakte in 2002 as part of a *Quealea* project of the Agricultural Research Council. Remarkably, 228 species in this collection suggest that there are probably many more, particularly in the massif. Most of these species are ground living, and the records are dominated by *Palpimanus transvaalicus*, *Camillina cordifera*, and *Diores recurvatus*.

Palpimanus transvaalicus P. Webb *Camillina cordifera* P. Webb

Recently, Prof. Nigel Barker and a consortium of researchers from various institutions successfully applied for an FBIP (Foundational Biodiversity Information Programme) grant from the NRF with the Waterberg massif as the target area. Surveys include an extensive range of 1000–2000 m a.s.l. The 2022/23 rainfall season saw Dr Caswell Munyai and his PhD student (Caroline Kunene) from the University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN) lead pitfall surveys in the Waterberg (Fig. 2).

The main purpose was to get a representative sample of ground-living arthropods in the region and tease apart the relative importance of elevation aspect, habitat structure, and area affecting the diversity of this important component of biodiversity. Replicates of ten pitfalls, left open for five days, were stratified across the massif. Of particular interest for spiders would be the effect of habitat structure and replicates, including paired samples of open and closed habitats (Fig. 3). Samples from the first survey in September have been processed at the University of Venda. They will be identified up to species level. The results of this study will also provide an interesting contrast with that of the Soutpansberg, which have similar elevational ranges but very different topography and climates.

Figure 3. Closed (background) and open (foreground) habitats sampled during the survey.

Figure 1. Distribution of sample sites and the number of records for spiders in the National Collection of Arachnida.

Figure 2. Distribution of sample sites across the Waterberg massif.

Contact: Stefan Foord at stefan@foord.co

“Another one bites the dust”

An *Euprosthenoopsis* sp. captured by a wasp. Photographs were taken by Allen Jones in the Free State.

More *Argiope australis* stories from the Free State

A. Jones & A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman
 allenjones@lantic.net and DippenaarAnsie@gmail.com

In a paper by Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones (2021) we discussed the behaviour of the garden orb-web spider *Argiope australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) as observed in Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the Free State, South Africa. We provided information on their somatic variation and some general behaviour.

These spiders typically have diurnal behaviour and are active during the day. However, when the weather permits, they are active at night as well. They remain on their webs, capturing any prey that becomes trapped. This species has solitary behavior, and only interacts with the opposite sex while breeding.

The first author (AJ) lives at Mpetsane Conservation Estate and is able to observe and photograph the spiders. He observed some interesting behaviour on how silk thread is used to construct stabilimenta in the webs, as well as moulting, mating behaviour, and web shaking. He also calculated that 64 m of silk threads is used to build a web.

STABILIMENTUM

The number of stabilimenta of *A. australis* vary from four to none. A large number (67%) of webs are seen without any. Their stabilimenta are not very dense and can vary from a central strip stretching upwards or downwards. Sometimes the spiders changed the stabilimenta format from a full X then a Y then just a vertical strip. Apparently, an X shape is not common for *Argiope australis*.

They remove the stabilimentum after dark as there is nothing in the web at first light. The new stabilimentum is put up in seconds (Figs 1-3). The female lays the bottom zigzag first (Fig. 4) and always lays the zigzag from outside to the hub inwards.

Figures 1–4. Female releasing bands of silk to add a stabilimentum to her orb-web. In Figure 3 the fine threads of thick aciniform silk can be seen that is used for decorating and prey wrapping.

WEB SHAKING

Very early every in the morning the spiders perform a “jig” dance in their web. They shake the web quite strongly; obviously they are tensioning and tuning the strands.

Figures 5–6. Spider vigorously shaking web early in the morning.

MOULTING AND MATING

A male was observed trying to mate with a female but eventually moved. . It was only after she had moulted that he was able to move closer to mate.

Figure 7. Male trying to mate, first attempt.

Figures 8–11. Male moving closer to mate after her last moult.

REFERENCE

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & JONES A. 2022. More on the garden orb-web spider *Argiope australis* (Walckenaer, 1805) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 40: 19–22.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915580>

All this information was shared with Prof. Alexander Kerr at the University of Guam who is preparing a paper on web decorations.
<https://www.uog.edu/directory/kerr-alexander.php>

PRESENTATIONS DEALING WITH SOUTH AFRICAN FAUNA PRESENTED AT THE 22nd INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS OF ARACHNOLOGY IN MONTEVIDEO, URUGUAY 2023

FONSECA-FERREIRA R., BRESCOVIT A.D., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LEITE G.J.P. 2023. Redelimitation of the genus *Idiops* Perty, 1833 (Idiopidae) and transfer of five species to the genus *Segregara* Tucker, 1917.

Trapdoor spiders of the genus *Idiops* Perty, 1833, (Idiopidae, Idiopinae) are traditionally diagnosed by presenting the combination of two complete rows of teeth in the basal segment of the chelicera, absence of spinules on the coxae, and two pairs of sternal sigilla. After preliminary phylogenomic analysis of Idiopidae, we propose that *Idiops* be redelimited to include only Neotropical species. These differ from the other genera by the presence of a row of large teeth on the chelicerae along the retromargin, small teeth on the chelicerae concentrated in the basal third of the promargin, absence of spinules on the coxae, and two pairs of sternal sigilla. Based on the examination of some African types belonging to Idiopinae and the new diagnosis of the genus *Idiops*, we propose the transfer of five species of *Idiops* to the genus *Segregara* Tucker, 1917. *Segregara* species can be characterised by the presence of spinules on the coxae, three pairs of sternal sigilli, and small posterior sternal sigilla. Thus, we present new combinations for *Segregara monticola* (Hewitt, 1916) comb. nov., *S. monticoloides* (Hewitt, 1919) comb. nov., *S. ochreolus* (Pocock, 1902) comb. nov., and *S. sylvestris* (Hewitt, 1925) comb. nov. from South Africa and *S. mossambicus* (Hewitt, 1919) comb. nov. from Mozambique and South Africa. We also emphasise the need to review the other species included in *Idiops*, especially for the African region, for the correct positioning in Idiopinae or even the proposition of new genera to accommodate these species.

FONSECA-FERREIRA R., SHAHAN D., VERA O., Lyle R., MORALES M.J.A. & LEITE G.J.P. 2023. Phylogenomics analysis of *Idiops* Perty, 1833 and Idiopinae Simon, 1889, based in ultraconserved elements (UCE): first results.

Among the Mygalomorphae spiders, Idiopidae is the second most diverse family, comprising exclusively trapdoor spiders, divided in three subfamilies: Arbanitinae, Genysinae, and Idiopinae. Mainly characterised by having the anterior lateral eyes projected in front of the others, the subfamily Idiopinae currently comprises 148 species, distributed in seven genera: the type-genus *Idiops*, composed of 96 valid species, plus *Ctenolophus*, *Galeosoma*, *Gorgyrela*, *Heligmomerus*, *Segregara*, and *Titanidiops*. Based on datasets composed of fresh and museum samples, we present the results of the first phylogenomic analysis based on Ultraconserved Elements (UCEs), which, for the first time, included species of *Idiops* from South America and Africa, representatives of all genera of Idiopinae, except *Galeosoma*, in addition to *Neocteniza*, an enigmatic genus of Genysinae. We generated phylogenetic trees (PHYLUC software, Spider2kv1 probe-set, Maximum Likelihood analyses) that aimed to test the monophyly of the genus *Idiops*, and the monophyly and intrarelations of Idiopinae. According to our results, the neotropical species of *Idiops* form a monophyletic clade distinct from the African species, which are more closely related to other African genera. In all analyses, the subfamily Idiopinae appeared as monophyletic and more phylogenetically related to *Cteniza* (Ctenizidae) than to *Neocteniza* (Idiopidae). Due to the position of *Neocteniza*, which for the first time is included in a molecular phylogeny,

Idiopidae is now considered a paraphyletic taxon. The results found for Idiopinae are morphologically supported mainly by the arrangement of the eyes. The division of *Idiops* into two clades is supported by the distinct dentition patterns of the chelicerae.

ČANDEK K., YU K-P., MATJAŽ G., AGNARSSON I. & KUNTNER M. 2023. *Megaraneus*: A new case of extreme sexual size dimorphism in araneid spiders.

Field research in little-explored regions such as parts of Africa promises the discovery of new or rare and poorly understood arachnids. Original descriptions of enigmatic species are often basic, lacking morphological details and assessment of variation. In spiders, numerous such taxa are yet to be placed phylogenetically, and their natural history remains unknown. In effect, such taxa are only placeholders in the catalogue, and there is a need to systematically uncover their taxonomic validity, document their biology, and interpret their evolutionary histories. During our fieldwork in South Africa, we documented the natural history of a conspicuous but poorly known araneid *Megaraneus gabonensis*. Our measurements of both sexes revealed a female to male size ratio of around 4. According to the literature, this ratio constitutes extreme sexual size dimorphism (eSSD). In araneid spiders, eSSD has evolved multiple times, but since *Megaraneus* has never been phylogenetically placed, we pose the question whether the eSSD evolution in *Megaraneus* is independent from the documented cases. We report on the phylogenetic test of this hypothesis using classical markers in an expanded araneid phylogenetic matrix. This test will have taxonomic implications and will elucidate *Megaraneus* eSSD in an evolutionary context. Individuals travelled through all the arena searching for an environment with lower salinity.

WILLIAMS P. & ABEL G.P. 2023. The newest and the oldest in the same jar: Redescription of *Ceratontia capensis* and description of a new species of *Ceratontia* for South Africa (Opiliones: Laniatores: Triaenonychidae).

Triaenonychidae Sørensen, 1886, is a family with ~126 species described in South Africa, and distribution in the temperate regions of the Global South that formed the supercontinent Gondwana. *Ceratontia* Roewer 1915, one of the most interesting Triaenonychidae genera with 18 species described for South Africa and four for South America, was formerly considered a transcontinental genus, but recent phylogenetic studies challenge this assumption and point to the non-monophyly of this genus. This work aims to redescribe the type species of *Ceratontia*, *Ceratontia capensis* Roewer, 1915, as a starting point for a future taxonomic revision of the genus. Examining the type series of *C. capensis* we found among the paratypes one specimen that belongs to a new species for science. As another result, we also provide a detailed description and illustration of this new species, which has distinct morphological and genital differences from the other species in the genus.

See also the next page for more aspects dealing with the 22nd International Congress of Arachnology.

RECENT PUBLICATIONS

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., BLAKE B. & WEBB P. 2023. Notes on the butterfly crab spider *Trichopagis manicata* Simon, 1886 in South Africa (Aranea: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 44: 17–19. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7539734.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2023. *The Prodidomidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 42 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7515818.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2023. *The Tetragnathidae of South Africa*. Version 2. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 50 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7513261.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & VAN ZYL J. 2023. First record of the theridiid spider *Rhomphaea affinis* Lessert, 1936 from South Africa (Arachnida: Theridiidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 44: 14–16. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7539731.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., VAN ZYL J., SANDER A., BLAKE B. & WEBB P. 2023. New information on the green tree crab spider *Oxytate argenteooculata* (Simon, 1886) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 44: 10–13. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7539729.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & WEBB P. 2023. Notes on the wolf spider *Hippasosa guttata* (Karsch, 1878) in South Africa (Araneae: Lycosidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 44: 20–22. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7539708.

KRONESTEDT T. 2023. Species of *Wadicosa* (Araneae, Lycosidae): Transfer of four species from Africa currently placed in *Pardosa*. *Zootaxa* 5227(5): 531–548.

RÍOS-TAMAYO D., LYLE R. & SOLE C.L. 2023. *Ekapa*, a new genus of mygalomorph spiders (Araneae, Entypesidae) from South Africa. *African Invertebrates* 64(1): 1–12.

International Society of Arachnology March, 2023 Montevideo Uruguay

Congratulations to all the newly elected committee members of the International Society of Arachnology (ISA).

We also want to congratulate Charles Griswold and Yael Lubin who have received the “**Simon Award**” for lifetime achievement. Both of them have a long association with South Africa.

***Charles Griswold:** Charles, Ansie, and the late Peter Croeser were the founding members of the African Arachnological Society in 1987. It was originally the Research Group for the Study of African Arachnida. The name was later changed to the African Arachnological Society (AFRAS) in 1996. Charles, while working at the Natal Museum, has made very important contributions with his taxonomic papers on the Cyatholipidae, Dictynidae, Drymusidae, Migidae, Microstigmatidae, Mysmenidae, Orsolobidae, and Phyxelididae.

***Yael Lubin:** Yael is involved in several ecological projects with Tharina Bird and Joh Henschel in South Africa. She regularly visits and has also attended some of the AFRAS colloquia.

***Also, congratulations to Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman** who received with three other arachnologists honorary membership of the society in recognition of her contribution to African Arachnology.

5th AFRAS Colloquium at Klein Kariba 1996 attended by Charles and Yael (white circles).

COMPLETED SPIDER PHOTO IDENTIFICATION GUIDES (2020-2023) AVAILABLE FROM THE WORLD SPIDER CATALOG AND ZENODO

<https://zenodo.org/communities/sansa/>

2020

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020a. *The Agelenidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 23 pp. [the 2nd pdf is version 2 from 2022, which differs only slightly and has no different doi] doi:10.5281/zenodo.5981186

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., & LOTZ L.N. 2020b. *The Ammoxenidae of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: 2020 version 1: 1-20. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5913561>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020c. *The Anapidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 12 pp. [the 2nd pdf is version 2 from 2022, which differs only slightly] doi:10.5281/zenodo.6759226

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020d. *The Anyphaenidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 6 pp. [the 2nd pdf is version 2 from 2022, which differs only slightly and has no different doi] doi:10.5281/zenodo.5982411

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020e. *The Atypidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 7 pp. [the 2nd pdf is version 2 from 2022, which differs only slightly and has no different doi] doi:10.5281/zenodo.6032638

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020f. *The Barychelidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 9 pp. [the 2nd pdf is version 2 from 2022, which differs only slightly and has no different doi] doi:10.5281/zenodo.603349

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020g. *The Caponiidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 24 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5913570

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020h. *The Cyatholipidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 27 pp. [the 2nd pdf is version 2 from 2022, which differs only slightly and has a different doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6759933] doi:10.5281/zenodo.6090255

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020i. *The Cyrtauchenidae of South Africa*. Version 1. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 37 pp. [the 2nd pdf is version 2 from 2022, which differs only slightly and has a different doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6760048] doi:10.5281/zenodo.6090510

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020j. *The Deinopidae of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, Version 1. 16 pp. [the 2nd pdf is version 2 from 2022, which differs only slightly and has no different doi] doi:10.5281/zenodo.6326965

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020k. *The Dictynidae of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, Version 1. 14 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6159874

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020l. *The Dysderidae of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, Version 1: 5 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6160063

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2020m. *The Hersiliidae of South Africa*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, Version 1: 23 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5913607

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1. Corinnidae pp. 65 (draft 1)
2. Entypesidae
3. Linyphiidae pp. 62 (draft 1)
4. Nesticidae
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6. Pholcidae pp. 64 (draft 1)
7. Pycnothelidae pp. 6 (draft 1)
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Salticidae part 2 (E-Ha) pp. 62 (draft 2)
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11. Zodariidae part 1 (draft 1)
10. Zoropsidae

The male of the spiny-back orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) (Araneae: Araneidae)

D. Pelsler¹, H. Heron¹ & A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman²

¹SANSA team members, KwaZulu-Natal; des@earthandoceans.co.za; hughheronescombe@gmail.com; ²University of Venda, dippenaaransie@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: Only the female of the spiny-back orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) was known. Some information on the first male collected and photographed in South Africa is provided.

Key words: Afrotropical, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, SANSA Virtual Museum, savanna, webs

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Afracantha* Dahl (1914) is a monotypic genus known only from Africa. The type species, *Afracantha camerunensis*, was described from Cameroon by Thorell (1899) as *Gasteracantha brevispina camerunensis*. The species is presently known from seven African countries: Cameroon, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ghana, Eswatini, Botswana, Zambia, and South Africa.

Notes on the female were provided by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2021) and the first notes on their web behaviour by Heron (2017). The species is well camouflaged and not easily seen and is regarded as rare in South Africa, although single specimens have so far been recorded from three provinces in South Africa.

The first author (DP) observed the female of the species for the first time in her garden in Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal, in 2020, where she was able to photograph the female as well as the orb-web (Fig. 1) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). Now, for the first time, she has observed and photographed the much smaller male (Figs 3-4) with a female (Fig. 2) in her garden.

MALE DESCRIPTION

TL size 5.6 mm. The male resembles the female in colour but differs in size and shape. The carapace is dark brown, with numerous scattered strong, white setae. The eye region differs from the female in being narrowed anteriorly; lateral eyes close together, situated on carapace border but widely spaced from median eyes; anterior and posterior median eyes closely grouped; anterior median eyes on a small tubercle; posterior median eyes slightly wider apart. Abdomen is wider than long, with an uneven surface and with two prominent lateral humps with rounded, white distal tips. The humps differ in size with the posterior one being the largest. The carapace is brown with scattered orange, white, and dark patches. The integument with numerous strong setae of which the colour varies from white to reddish brown. Anterior edge rounded, dorsally bearing 14 dark sigillae. A double row of sigillae are arranged in rows medially. The legs are short and stocky and bear numerous clusters of the white, strong setae.

LIFESTYLE

On two occasions the orb-web of *A. camerunensis* was spotted in KwaZulu-Natal. The first was in a campsite in an open area of mown grassland dotted with *Vachellia* trees in the Umgeni Valley (Heron, 2017; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). The spider was suspended in a vertically oriented colourless orb-web with a diameter of about 20 cm and supported by a long bridge line about half a metre wide below an overhead branch of *Vachellia nilotica*.

Figures 1–3. *Afracantha camerunensis* from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal. 1. Orb-web. 2. Female. 3. Male. Photo credits: Desiré Pelsler.

Figures 4–6. *Afracantha camerunensis* from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal. 4–5. Male. 6. Female, on bark, blending in with environment. Photo credits: Desiré Pelsler.

OBSERVATIONS

First sighting: The first sighting (March, 2017) of *A. camerunensis* was in the Umgeni Valley (Heron, 2017). The female was in an orb-web with two companion spiders, smaller in size. They were on both sides of the female but not in their own webs. The author later speculated that it might have been males.

Second sighting: The female was sighted in March, 2021, by the first author (PS) in an orb-web about 2.0 m from the ground in Kloof in KwaZulu-Natal (Fig. 1). A redescription of the female was provided by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2021).

Third sighting: A female was photographed on 27 January, 2023 by the first author (DP) from the same tree that the second female was found in 2021 (Fig. 6). The female was seen the whole day and with the female was a very tiny spider that turned out to be the male (Figs 3–5). Below the web a bundle of prey debris covered with silk hang (Fig. 7). The purpose is unclear unless it is an egg sac covered by debris.

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Figure 7. *Afracantha camerunensis* female from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal. Photo credit: Desiré Pelsler

First record of the trash-line spider *Cyclosa conica* (Pallas, 1772) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & J. van Zyl²

¹ Department of Zoology, University of Venda, dippenaaransie@gmail.com. ² SANSA team member, Gauteng, johan.gailvz@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: We present the first records of the trash-line spider *Cyclosa conica* (Pallas, 1772) from South Africa. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed with notes on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Cyclosa* Menge, 1866 is a large genus known from 177 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog, 2023). The African *Cyclosa* species have not yet been revised and only three species are presently recorded from Africa and only two are listed from South Africa.

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), a large number of specimens from several localities in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) were sampled. However, a large percentage of Araneidae specimens sampled is difficult to identify to species level. While working through the SANSA Virtual Museum photographic database, a female specimen in her trash line web was positively identified as *Cyclosa conica* (Pallas, 1772). Features of the species were compared with illustrations and the original description of the species.

Cyclosa conica is a small orb weaver that is easily recognised by the shape of the abdomen. The species is very widely spread and is known from North America, Europe, to the Far East. It is here for the first time recorded from South Africa where it was sampled from KwaZulu-Natal, but more unidentified specimens are possibly housed in natural history collections in South Africa.

TAXONOMY

In the World Spider Catalog (2023), more than 50 references are listed for *C. conica*. Total length of females 4-7 mm and males 3-5. The female can be recognised by the shape and colour of the abdomen. Abdomen bulging anteriorly, with large angular tubercle posteriorly, sometimes with additional smaller humps; caudal hump can vary in length; dorsum decorated with indistinct brownish pattern (Figs 1–3); legs pale, with indistinct dark bands at tip of most segments. Epigyne with sclerotised lobe on each side of scape; scape of epigynum tapered toward posterior end (Fig. 5). In male, carapace brownish, somewhat paler anteriorly, strongly narrowed toward front. Legs pale, with indistinct dark bands; tibia II somewhat stouter and with somewhat longer macrosetae than tibia I; coxa IV with 1 or 2 small macrosetae ventrally (Fig. 4). Male palp with median apophysis heavily sclerotised and its distal tip folded over (Fig. 6) (Levi, 1977).

LIFE STYLE

The name “*Cyclosa*” comes from the Greek “to move in a circle” and refers to how it spins its web. They make a complete vertical, closely woven orb-web in vegetation, about one metre above the ground. The distinguishing character of the web is the vertical stabilimentum that runs down the centre of the web, in line with the hub (Fig. 2).

Figures 1–2. *Cyclosa conica* female in orb-web from Pinetown
Photo credits: Johan van Zyl.

Figures 3–6. *Cyclosa conica* line drawings. 3. Female lateral view. 4. Male lateral view. 5. Epigyne. 6. Male palp. Credits: After Levi (1977).

The female in her web was found on a shrub. The orb is wider than long, with 40 to 50 radii (Fig. 7) and it lacks a retreat. The stabilimentum is composed of dead prey and other debris that are woven together with silk (Fig. 8). The spider hides in this debris as a defense against predators (Fig. 2). The spider hangs in the centre with legs folded around the body (Fig. 1). The natural coloration of members of *Cyclosa* makes it extremely difficult to see, and only when it moves, the spider is spotted (Figs 7–8) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022a).

According to Dondale (2002), mature males do not build orb-webs. The females produce three to five egg sacs that are elliptical, yellowish brown, and are attached to dead twigs or under leaves, but not to the orb-web.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

North America, Europe, Turkey, Caucasus, Russia, Iran, Central Asia, China. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

KwaZulu-Natal: Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85).

CONSERVATION STATUS

Due to wide global range listed as Least Concern.

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Figures 7–8. *Cyclosa conica* female photographed on 7 March, 2020 in an orb-web in Pinetown, KwaZulu-Natal. Photo credits Johan van Zyl.

First record of the crab spider *Diaea longisetosa* Roewer, 1961 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & P. Webb²

¹ Department of Zoology, University of Venda, dippenaaransie@gmail.com. ² SANSA team member, Gauteng (deceased)

Abstract: The male of the crab spider *Diaea longisetosa* Roewer, 1961 was described from Senegal in Africa. It is for the first time recorded from South Africa and the general morphology of the male is discussed with photographs of live specimens provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Diaea* Thorell, 1869 is presently known from 46 species and three species are listed from South Africa (World Spider Catalogue, 2023). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large areas in South Africa were surveyed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and several *Diaea* species have been collected. One of these species has been identified as *Diaea longisetosa*, an African endemic described by Roewer (1961) from Senegal, with only the male known. In the present paper the male is redescribed and new distribution records for the species are added, as well as notes on their behaviour and conservation status.

METHODS

Material was obtained from the SANSA surveys and voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. Additional information was obtained from the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Diaea longisetosa Roewer, 1961

Diaea longisetosa Roewer, 1961: 76, f. 29a-g (Dm).

Diagnostic characteristics: Male (Figs 1–2): body size 4 mm. Carapace longer than wide, narrowed in eye region; integument pale green with darker green lateral and marginal bands; eye region with eyes covered by brown patch; eyes in two recurved rows on slight tubercles, lateral eyes larger than median eyes (Figs 4 & 8); carapace with dark, long setae scattered dorsally and on clypeal edge. Sternum heart shaped. Legs I and II much longer than III and IV; all legs pale green with scattered dark setae; legs I and II with darker markings on femora I where three setae have a dark brown base giving it a spotted appearance; dark bands present on legs I and II between trochanter and tibiae and distally on tibiae and metatarsi (Fig. 9). Abdomen oval with cream base and numerous dark setae (Figs 3 & 7); dorsally decorated with brown patterns that are edged with red marking. Male palp pale green with tarsus brown; retro-tibial apophysis long and pointed; median apophysis spade-like and ventral apophysis small (Figs 5–6). It resembles members of *Heriaeus*.

Female unknown but an immature specimen sampled from the same locality as the male at Lephahlale possibly belongs to the same species. The basic colour resembles that of the male but the dark brown patterns on the carapace and abdomen and bands on legs are absent. Body and legs pale green, abdomen with faint pattern (Fig. 10).

Figures 1–2. *Diaea longisetosa* male from Lephahlale, Limpopo. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 3–6. *Didea longisetosa* male. 3. Habitus dorsal view. 4. Eye pattern. 5-6. Male palp. Credits: After Roewer (1961).

LIFE STYLE

Didea longisetosa is a free-living plant dweller. Specimens were sampled while sweeping grassland in the Savanna biome during a BioBlitz on the farm Zandrivier, approximately 10 km south of Lephalale (Ellisras) in the Waterberg Biosphere Reserve (Webb & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Senegal. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Limpopo: Farm Zandrivier 14 km south of Lephalale (23°48'29.43S, 27°46'26.41E).

CONSERVATION

An African endemic known from Senegal in the north and South Africa in the south. This species is possibly under-collected and suspected to occur in more localities. Due to its wide global range it is listed as Least Concern.

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Figures 7–10. *Didea longisetosa*. 7. Male habitus dorsal view. 8. Eye pattern. 9. Dorsal views showing the leg markings. 10. Immature specimen, possibly undescribed female of species. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

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WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2023. World Spider Catalog. Version 24. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 13 March 2023. doi: 10.24436/2

First record of the crab spider *Diaea albicincta* Pavesi, 1883 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, L. Wiese² & R. Steenkamp³

¹ Department of Zoology, University of Venda ²; SANSA Team member Eastern Cape; ³ SANSA Team member Free State

Abstract: The African crab spider *Diaea albicincta* is known from Ethiopia and Tanzania. It is now for the first time recorded from South Africa. The general morphology is discussed with photographs of live specimens provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation status are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Diaea* Thorell, 1869 is presently known from 46 species and three species are listed from South Africa (World Spider Catalogue, 2023). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) large areas in South Africa was surveyed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and several *Diaea* species have been collected. One of these species has been identified as *Diaea albicincta*, an African endemic described by Pavesi (1883) from Ethiopia from a male. Lessert (1919) described another male and the female from Mount Meru and Viboscho in Tanzania.

It is for the first time recorded from South Africa and the general morphology is discussed with photographs of live specimens provided as well as notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation status.

METHODS

Material was obtained from the SANSA surveys and voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA). Additional information was obtained from the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Diaea albicincta Pavesi, 1883

Diaea albicincta Pavesi, 1883: 61 (m); Lessert, 1919: 141, f. 18–19, pl. 2, f. 31, 44 (m, f).

Diagnostic characters: Male (Figs 1 & 4) and female (Figs 2–3, 10 & 11). Body size: female 6–7 mm; male 5–6 mm. Male resemble the female but sometimes more brightly coloured. Carapace green with only the eye region covered by a brown patch; chelicerae green in female, in male with dark tint (Fig. 1). Abdomen oval, longer than wide; green with broad yellow-white area cover most of dorsal area; impose over the white area, abdomen decorated with a dark leaf like pattern that vary in shape between specimens, pattern usually edged with red brown. In a female collected at Wakefield farm, Kwa Zulu-Natal the specimen without distinct pattern on abdomen (Fig. 11). Legs green with a yellowish tint. In adults the legs I and II usually with distal end of leg segments with dark brown bands. In some males the femora ventrally with dark tint (Fig. 1). In immature specimens (Figs 11–12) the front legs without brown bands.

LIFE STYLE

Diaea albicincta is a free-living plant dweller that are active during the day. With their green colour they blend in with the vegetation.

Figures 1–3. *Diaea albicincta* 1 Male and 2. Female from Addo Elephant National Park. 3. Female from Karkloof. Photo credits: 1–2. Linda Wiese. 3. Rudi Steenkamp.

Figure 4–9. *Diaea albicincta* 4. Male habitus. 5–6. Male palp. 7. Female abdomen. 8. Epigyne. 9. Eye pattern.
Credits: 4–8 After Lessert (1919). 9. Peter Webb.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Ethiopia, Tanzania, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park, Woody Cape (-33.88, 26.45) (Species was wrongly identified as *Diaea viridipes*); Gqeberha (Port Elizabeth) (-33.95, 25.61).

KwaZulu-Natal: Hillcrest, Farm Wakefield (-29.5, 29.90); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Karkloof (-29.30, 30.27). **Western Cape:** Gondwana Game Reserve, SE Herbertsdale (-34.07, 21.9); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

CONSERVATION

An African endemic known from Ethiopia and Tanzania in the north and South Africa in the south. This species is under-collected and suspected to occur in more countries. Due to its wide range it is listed as Least Concern with no known threats.

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Figure 10–12. *Diaea albicincta*. 10. Female habitus from Kloof. 11. Immature female from Gondwana Game Reserve. 12. Immature female from Wakefield. Photo credits: 10. Bruce Blake. 11. 12. Peter Webb.

SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Jeffreys Bay, South Africa

L. Wiese¹ & A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman²

¹SANSA team member, Eastern Cape, Jeffrey's Bay, South Africa, lwiese9@gmail.com; ²Department of Zoology, University of Venda, South Africa, dippenaaransie@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), several surveys were undertaken in the Eastern Cape. In this paper, an annotated species list of spiders species sampled from Jeffreys Bay is presented. A total of 38 families represented by 151 species from 101 genera have been recorded. The most species-rich families are the Araneidae (27 spp.), Thomisidae (23 spp.), and Salticidae (16 spp.). The conservation status and level of endemicity based on their known distribution are provided for each species.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation assessment, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

World-wide, the loss of biodiversity and the increasing growth of the urban world population are some of the main challenges of this century. Interest in the invertebrate fauna of urban and suburban areas has increased in the last 20 years. These areas are not just seen as human-modified habitats of low intrinsic biodiversity, but as havens for wildlife in an increasingly intensively farmed and over-managed countryside. These areas can be potential corridors for dispersal of wildlife through urban areas, promoting connectivity between species' meta-populations both within and outside towns and cities.

Unfortunately, the evidence for these effects on spiders in South Africa is either anecdotal or lacking. Little has been published on spiders of urban and suburban areas. Tucker (1920) was the first to report on the spiders of Kirstenbosch in the Western Cape. Other Western Cape studies supported initiatives to remove alien pines in urban areas and highlight the conservation value of urban botanical gardens of indigenous plants (Pryke & Samways, 2009). In Gauteng, one of the surveys in urban areas includes a three-year study at the Rietondale Research Station, an area close to the centre of Pretoria, by Van den Berg and Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991). In Kwa-Zulu-Natal, Clark and Samways (1997) studied arthropods, including spiders, in a botanical garden in Pietermaritzburg, while Whitmore *et al.* (2002) investigated arthropod diversity on road islands in Durban, where they found that spider abundance was markedly higher on grassy road islands that were regularly mowed than on structurally enhanced road islands. In the Free State, several studies have been undertaken in the Free State National Botanical Garden, Bloemfontein (Butler & Haddad, 2011; Neethling & Haddad, 2013). For the Eastern Cape, this is the first report of a spider survey in an urban area.

In the Eastern Cape, several surveys from protected areas have been published (Table 1). Most of the abovementioned surveys form part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) for protected areas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

In this paper we present the first SANSA survey on the spider fauna sampled from an urban garden (Fig. 3) and surrounding areas in Jeffreys Bay in the Eastern Cape (Figs 1–2). Information on endemicity and conservation status for 148 species is provided.

Figures 1–3. Jeffreys Bay. 1-2. Noorsekloof. 3. Garden. Photo credits: Linda Wiese.

TABLE 1. Results of SANSa spider surveys in the Eastern Cape

LOCALITY	FAM	SPP	REFERENCES
Mountain Zebra National Park	34	76	Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988; 2006
Addo Elephant National Park	47	276	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Mkambati Nature Reserve	29	132	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2011
Silaka Nature Reserve		11	Forbanka & Niba, 2013
Asante Sana Nature Reserve	29	92	Midgley, 2012 (unpublished)
Thyspunt	26	94	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2021
Amathole Mountains	52	321	Haddad <i>et al.</i> (under review)
Jeffreys Bay	38	149	

METHODS

Study area: Jeffreys Bay (JB)(34°2'S 24°55'E, 34°2'S 24°55'E) is a constituent part of the Kouga Local Municipality of the Sarah Baartman District in the Eastern Cape province. The vegetation of the area consists of fynbos and subtropical vegetation known as Valley Bushveld, a broad term given to the subtropical transitional thickets of the Eastern Cape that are mostly seen in the hot, dry valleys of rivers. The vegetation is usually made up of thorny, dense vegetation or succulent shrubs (Figs 1 & 2). At the seashore (Fig. 4) intertidal spiders were sampled.

Figure 4. Survey area Jeffreys Bay, Eastern Cape.

Figure 5. Jeffreys Bay coastline where *Amaurobioides africana* (Anyphaenidae) (Fig. 21) was sampled.

Identification, photography and voucher specimens: Identifications were done in Pretoria by the second author (ASD) and the voucher specimens are housed in the NCA at the Agricultural Research Council-Plant Health and Protection division in Pretoria. Some of the species could not be identified to species level because only immature specimens were sampled or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved (Table 4). The photographs were donated to the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Endemicity: The endemicity values for each species were determined (Table 3) based on their currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised:

- 6 = when Jeffreys Bay is the type locality.
- 5 = ECE, endemic to the Eastern Cape province but wider than the type locality.

TABLE 2: Spider diversity of Jeffreys Bay listing the total number of families, genera (G), and species (SPP.)

FAMILY	G	SPP.	FAMILY	G	SPP.
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Anyphaenidae	1	1	Philodromidae	2	2
Araneidae	18	27	Pholcidae	2	3
Cheiracanthiidae	2	4	Phyxelididae	1	2
Clubionidae	1	3	Pisauridae	2	2
Corinnidae	2	2	Prodidomidae	1	1
Ctenidae	1	1	Salticidae	12	16
Cyatholipidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Deinopidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Desidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	2
Dictynidae	1	1	Sparassidae	2	3
Eresidae	2	2	Stasimopidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	2	5	Tetragnathidae	3	6
Hahniidae	1	2	Theridiidae	7	9
Hersiliidae	1	1	Thomisidae	10	23
Linyphiidae	4	4	Trachelidae	2	2
Lycosidae	3	3	Uloboridae	2	2
Mimetidae	2	3	Zodariidae	1	1
Oxyopidae	3	9	Zoropsidae	1	1
			38	101	151

- 4 = SAE, endemic to South Africa but known from only two adjoining provinces.
- 3 = SAE, South African endemic, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining.
- 2 = STHE, endemic to Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene rivers).
- 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African endemic).
- 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 151 species from 38 families and 101 genera are presently known from Jeffreys Bay. Nine species could not be identified to species level as their taxonomy is unresolved or it could be new. Two species of the species sampled have already been recognised as new to science: *Cheiramiona lindae* Lotz, 2015 (Fig. 6, Cheiracanthiidae) and *Mystaria lindaicapensis* Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014 (Figs 7–8, Thomisidae). The oxyopid, *Oxyopes dumonti* (Vinson, 1863) was also for the first time recorded from South Africa at Jeffreys Bay (Wiese, 2008, Fig. 34).

Family diversity: Of the 38 spider families collected from Jeffreys Bay (Tables 2 & 4), the Araneidae (27 spp.) followed by the Thomisidae (23 spp.) and Salticidae with 16 species are the most diverse families. Thirteen of the species collected are known from only a single species.

TABLE 3: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species recorded from Jeffreys Bay.

CONSERVATION STATUS	No. spp.	Code	%
Data deficient (DD)	9	DD	5.9
Not evaluated (NE)	10	NE	6.2
Least concern (LC)	130	LC	86.0
Vulnerable (V)	1	VU	0.7
ENDEMICITY			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	19	LC	12.5
1 – African endemics (AE)	86	LC	56.9
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	26	LC	17.2
3 – South African endemics (SAE): more than three provinces	20	LC	13.2
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	9	LC	6.0
4 – <i>Mystaria lindaicapensis</i> Easter and Western Cape endemics (ECE)	1	VU	0.7
6 – <i>Cheiramiona lindae</i> Type locality (Jeffreys Bay)	1	DDT	0.7

Conservation status: The majority of species (130; 86%) have a wide distribution and no threats are known and they are listed as Least Concern. Nine species are Data Deficient as some are only known from one sex and other have a very restricted distribution. Ten was not evaluated as some the where immature or taxonomy not resolved.

Cheiramiona lindae (Cheiracanthiidae), an Eastern Cape endemic (Fig. 6), is presently known only from a single male sampled in 2008 in a garden in Jeffreys Bay (Lotz, 2015). Too little is known about the location, habitat, and threats of this species for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed to find the female and determine the species' range. It is therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic purposes.

The thomisid *Mystaria lindaicapensis* (Figs 7 & 8) is a species newly described from the garden in Jeffrey Bay (Honiball Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014). It was also recoded from Knysna but it has a small distribution range (< 20 000 km²) and is regarded as Vulnerable.

Endemism: Nineteen species (12.5%) are wider known than Africa, while 86 species (56.9%) have a wider distribution throughout Africa (AE), with 26 species (17.2 %) known from Southern Africa (STHE) and only 20 (13.2 %) are South African endemics.

Figures 7–8. *Mystaria lindaicapensis*. 7. Female. 8. Male.

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Figures 9–21. 9–20. Araneidae: 9. *Araneus apricus*. 10. *Araneus nigroquadratus*. 11. *Caerostris sexcupidata*. 12. *Cyclosa insulana*. 13. *Cyrtophora citricola*. 14. *Gea infuscata*. 15. *Ideocaira triquetra*. 16. *Isoxya cicatricosa*. 17. *Neoscona quincasea*. 18. *Neoscona alberti*. 19. *Neoscona rufipalpis*. 20. *Zygiella* sp. 21. *Amaurobioides africana* (Anyphaenidae). 22. *Gandanameno spenceri* (Eresidae). 23. *Quamtana vidal* (Pholcidae).

Figures 24–37. Jeffreys Bay spiders. 24–29. Thomisidae: 24. *Phrynarachne rugosa*. 25. *Diaea rohani*. 26. *Tmarus cancellatus*. 27. *Thomisus scrupeus*. 28. *Thomisus daradioides*. 29. *Synema langheldi*. 30. *Euryopis funebris* (Theridiidae). 31. *Philoponella angolensis* (Uloboridae). 32. *Mecynidis dentipalpis* (Linyphiidae). 33. *Phanotea cavata* (Zoropsidae). 34. *Oxyopes dumonti* (Oxyopidae). 35. *Uloborus plumipes* (Uloboridae). 36. *Stasimopus schoenlandi* (Stasimopidae). 37. *Afroceceto martini* (Trachelidae).

TABLE 4: Checklist of the spiders species recorded from Jeffreys Bay in the Eastern Cape with information on their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEND). * possibly new species or new record.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Amaurobiidae	<i>Chresiona</i> sp.		NE	
Anyphaenidae	<i>Amaurobioides africana</i> Hewitt, 1917	2	LC	STHE
Araneidae	<i>Acusilas africanus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Araneus nigroquadratus</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Araneus</i> cf. <i>detrimentosus</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889)		NE	
	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE
	<i>Gea infuscata</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ideocaira transversa</i> Simon, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ideocaira triquetra</i> Simon, 1903	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Isoxya tabulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinia chloris</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
	<i>Lariniodes</i> sp.		NE	
	<i>Neoscona alberti</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona penicillipes</i> (Karsch, 1879)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona quincasea</i> Roberts, 1983	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C
	<i>Paralarinia bartelsi</i> (Lessert, 1933)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zygiella</i> sp. (Clerck, 1757)		NE	
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona amarifontis</i> Lotz, 2002	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona lindae</i> Lotz, 2015 *type	6	DD	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona paradisis</i> Lotz, 2003	2	LC	STHE
Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
	<i>Clubiona godfreyi</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
	<i>Clubiona kiboschensis</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
Corinnidae	<i>Coenoptychus tropicalis</i> (Haddad, 2004)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	3	LC	SAE
Ctenidae	<i>Ctenus gulosus</i> Des Arts, 1912	2	LC	STHE
Cyatholipidae	<i>Cyatholipus quadrimaculatus</i> Simon, 1894	4	LC	SAE
Deinopidae	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
Desidae	<i>Badumna longinqua</i> (L. Koch, 1867)	0	LC	C
Dictynidae	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.		NE	
Eresidae	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE
Gnaphosidae	<i>Xerophaeus crustosus</i> Purcell, 1907	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Zelotes capsula</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes invidus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
Hahniidae	<i>Hahnia clathrata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
Hersiliidae	<i>Neotama corticola</i> (Lawrence, 1937)	3	LC	SAE
Linyphiidae	<i>Mecynidis dentipalpis</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1879)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE
Lycosidae	<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
Mimetidae	<i>Anansi natalensis</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Ero lawrencei</i> Unzicker, 1966	2	LC	STHE
Oxyopidae	<i>Hamataliwa rostrifrons</i> (Lawrence, 1928)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hamataliwa strandi</i> (Lessert, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hamataliwa</i> sp.		NE	
	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes dumonti</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Oxyopes vogelsangeri</i> Lessert, 1946	1	LC	AE
	<i>Peucetia maculifera</i> Pocock, 1900	2	LC	STHE
Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus globulifer</i> Simon, 1893	3	DD	SAE
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana vidal</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus dehoop</i> Huber, 2012	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
Phyxelididae	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Vidole lyra</i> Griswold, 1990	3	LC	SAE
Pisauridae	<i>Afropisaura ducis</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
Prodidomidae	<i>Theuma schreineri</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
Salticidae	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus demonstrativus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Massagris mirifica</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Menemerus bivittatus</i> (Dufour, 1831)	0	LC	C
	<i>Myrmarachne marshalli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Phlegra imperiosa</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thyenula juvenca</i> Simon, 1902	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Tusitala hirsuta</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes silvatica</i> Purcell 1904	4	LC	SAE
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna</i> sp.		NE	
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Anyphops stauntoni</i> (Pocock, 1902)	1	LC	AE
Sparassidae	<i>Palystes leppanae</i> Pocock, 1902	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Parapalystes</i> sp. imm.		NE	
Stasimopidae	<i>Stasimopus schoenlandi</i> Pocock, 1900	5	DD	SAE
Tetragnathidae	<i>Diphya simoni</i> Kauri, 1950	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Leucauge argyrescens</i> Benoit, 1978	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge medjensis</i> Lessert, 1930	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge thomeensis</i> Kraus, 1960	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tetragnatha nitens</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
Theridiidae	<i>Argyrodes argyrodes</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	0	LC	C
	<i>Argyrodes zonatus</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Phoroncidia capensis</i> (Simon, 1895)	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Platnickina mneon</i> (Bösenberg & Strand, 1906)	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
Thomisidae	<i>Ansiae tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Mystaria lindaicapensis</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014*	4	VU	SAE
	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxytate ribes</i> (Jézéquel, 1964)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Phrynarachne rugosa</i> (Latreille, 1804)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
	<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema langheldi</i> Dahl, 1907	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema mandibulare</i> Dahl, 1907	2	LC	AE
	<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema riflense</i> Strand, 1909	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus cancellatus</i> Thorell, 1899	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus natalensis</i> Lessert, 1925	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xysticus tugelanus</i> Lawrence, 1942	2	LC	STHE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Trachelidae	<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trachelas</i> sp.		NE	
Uloboridae	<i>Philoponella angolensis</i> (Lessert, 1933)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
Zodariidae	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900	4	LC	SAE
Zoropsidae	<i>Phanotea cavata</i> Griswold, 1994	4	LC	SAE

A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve, South Africa

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹

¹ Department of Zoology, University of Venda, Thohoyandou, South Africa, dippenaaransie@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

An annotated species list of spiders presently known from the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve in the North West province, South Africa, is provided. The checklist was compiled from data collected from the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) database. A total of 222 species from 40 families and 152 genera are presently protected in the reserve. The most species-rich families are the Thomisidae (36 spp.), Salticidae (33 spp.) and Araneidae (26 spp.), while 11 families are represented by singletons. The global distribution, endemism, and conservation status for each species is provided. Ninety-eight percent of the species have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern. Approximately 6.8% of the total South African spider fauna is protected in the reserve, and 19.8% of the species recorded are South African endemics.

Key words: South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), conservation, endemism, North West province, Savanna Biome

INTRODUCTION

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) was initiated in 1997 with the main aim to discover, describe, and make an inventory of the South African arachnid fauna. Species distribution data were essential information needed for the conservation assessments to compile a Red Data List of the Arachnida of South Africa. It is also important to have a record of endemic species, and species that are already receiving some protection in existing reserves and parks (McGeoch *et al.*, 2011).

The North West province covers 9.5% of the surface of South Africa. Only 2087 records of spiders from 89 sites are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and large areas still need to be sampled. Some extensive sampling of spiders in North West were undertaken in conventionally cultivated cotton fields (Van den Berg *et al.*, 1990; Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999) where 31 families and 127 species were sampled. Data on all the arachnid orders in the SANSa database were used to prepare a report on the diversity of arachno-fauna in the North West province (Power, 2014).

To date, 380 spp. from 52 families are known from the province (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Very few large-scale surveys have been undertaken in the province, and the only long-term survey in the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR) is reported on here. The current study presents the results of data from the SANSa database on the spiders sampled in the KMR in the North West province. It includes information on the species' global distribution, endemism, and conservation status.

METHODS

Study area: The North West province lies in the north of South Africa on the Botswana border, fringed by the Kalahari Desert in the west, Gauteng province to the east, and the Free State province to the south. With a total area of 106 512 square kilometres, North West is the country's fourth smallest province, taking up 8.7% of South Africa's land area with a population of 3.5 million people.

Much of the province consists of flat areas of scattered trees and grassland. The Magaliesberg mountain range in the northeast extends about 130 km from Pretoria to Rustenburg.

Figures 1–2. 1. Entrance to the reserve. 2. Habitat at the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR). Photo credits: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Magaliesberg Protected Natural Environment, about 100 km from Pretoria and Johannesburg. Originally established on the farm Rietvallei, which once belonged to President Paul Kruger, it has been gradually expanded over the years and now covers some 4500 ha. Temperatures range from 17 °C to 31 °C in the summer and from 3 °C to 21 °C in the winter. Annual rainfall totals about 360 mm, with almost all of it falling during the summer months, between October and April.

The reserve lies in the Savanna Biome, south-west of the town of Rustenburg. The land was proclaimed in 1967. It is situated on the northern slopes and summit of the Magaliesberg Mountain. The reserve is dominated by the rocky ridges of the Magaliesberg, with well-wooded ravines on the rugged slopes.

The Waterkloof River has its source here and runs through a reed basin. A large valley basin and an extensive plateau form an important water catchment area from which the main watercourse flows into a large, reed-filled marsh. Although broadly defined as sour bushveld, the reserve's vegetation is varied, comprising grassland, scrub, mixed woodland, and even scattered pockets of fynbos.

Sampling methods and identification: Spiders have been collected once a month over a period of four years from the KMR using beating, sweep-netting, and active search. The survey was monthly undertaken over a single day, therefore no pitfall traps were used. Sampling was done by members of the ARC Biosystematics' Arachnology team. Most samples were collected between 09h30 and 13h00. All the material collected has been deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA), Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria. The material was made available for taxonomic research, resulting in a large number of specimens being identified to species level.

FIGURE 3: Map showing location of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR).

Species endemism and conservation: The conservation status of species is important, and as part of the first edition of the Spider Atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010), an endemism index was provided for each species. It was calculated based on current distribution, which included six endemism categories, ranging from: 6 = endemic, known only from type locality / one locality only (Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMRE)); 5 = known from North West province only, wider than type locality (NWE); 4 = known from two adjoining provinces only; 3 = South Africa, > two provinces or not adjoining (South African endemic, SAE); 2 = Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers) (Southern African endemic, STHE); 1 = Afrotropical Region (African Endemic, AE); 0 = Africa and wider (Cosmopolitan, C).

Regarding conservation status, species that were only recorded from immatures or those that represent possible new species or undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE); species known from only one sex, old material, and not revised are data deficient either for taxonomic reasons (DDT) or lack distribution data (DD). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of Least Concern (LC); those of categories 3–5 are South African endemics (SAE), and based on their distribution ranges, most of them are also LC. The species in categories 5–6 are North West endemics (NWE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 40 families represented by 152 genera and 222 species have been collected from KMR (Table 1; Appendix 1). These are the first published results of long-term surveys undertaken in the North West province. In this survey, the Thomisidae (36 spp.), Salticidae (33 spp.), and Araneidae (26 spp.) were the most species-rich families (Table 1). There was a very high proportion of singleton families (11), i.e., represented by a single species only.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR) with total number of families, genera (G) and species (S) sampled.

FAMILY	G	S	FAMILY	G	S
Agelenidae	2	2	Oxyopidae	3	9
Araneidae	19	26	Palpimanidae	1	1
Barychelidae	1	1	Philodromidae	4	7
Caponiidae	1	1	Pholcidae	2	2
Cheiracanthiidae	1	3	Phyxelididae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	1	Pisauridae	4	4
Corinnidae	4	4	Prodidomidae	1	3
Cyrtachenidiidae	1	3	Salticidae	21	33
Deinopidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	2
Dictynidae	1	1	Sicariidae	2	2
Entypesidae	1	1	Sparassidae	4	4
Eresidae	2	3	Tetragnathidae	2	4
Gallieniellidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	5	5
Gnaphosidae	11	20	Theridiidae	9	10
Hersiliidae	2	3	Thomisidae	18	36
Idiopidae	2	2	Trachelidae	2	2
Linyphiidae	3	3	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Lycosidae	7	8	Uloboridae	2	2
Migidae	1	1	Zodariidae	3	5
Oecobiidae	3	3			
Oonopidae	1	1	40 fam	152	222

Species endemism and conservation status: Of the 222 species sampled, 3 spp. (1.5 %) are data deficient (DD), i.e., lacking taxonomic or distribution data, while only one *Archaeodictyna* sp. (undetermined) was not evaluated (NE) (Table 2; Appendix 1). The majority of the species (217 spp., 98 %) sampled are listed as being of least concern (LC)

A large percentage of species have a wide distribution throughout Africa. A total of 22 spp. (9.8 %) are found in countries outside Africa; 104 spp. (46.8 %) are African endemics; 51 spp. (23 %) are endemic to Southern Africa, and only 44 spp. (19.8 %) are South African endemics.

There are presently no endemic species recorded from KMR and none of the species are North West endemics. Only *Paroecobius nicolai* Wunderlich, 1995 (Oecobiidae) (Fig. 18) is near endemic and has also been recorded from Limpopo and *Theuma schultzei* Purcell, 1908 (Prodidomidae) from Northern Cape. One of the species, *Evarcha flagellaris* Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011, collected at KMR, was listed as part of the type series.

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR).

DISTRIBUTION	SPP.	%
CONSERVATION STATUS		
Data Deficient (DD)	3	1.5
Not Evaluated (NE)	1	0.5
Least Concern (LC)	217	98
Rare	0	
Near Threatened	0	
Vulnerable	0	
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	22	9.9
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	104	46.8
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	51	23
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	44	19.8
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	3	1.4
5 – North West endemics (NWE)	0	0.5
6 – Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR)	0	0

CONCLUSION

As signatories to the Convention on Biological Diversity, South Africa is obliged to develop a strategic plan for the conservation and sustainable utilisation of the diverse and species-rich fauna and flora. Preliminary investigations into the biodiversity of the invertebrate fauna in South Africa have highlighted the dilemma caused by a lack of baseline information on the ecology and diversity of most arachnid groups (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2002). Each survey contributes to our knowledge on the geographical distribution of spider species. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research. The contribution of existing reserves can only be highlighted through studies such as this.

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FIGURE 4: Selected spiders from the Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR). (4) *Pycnacantha tribulus* (Araneidae). (5) *Cyrtophora citricola* (Araneidae). (6) *Araneus apricus* (Araneidae). (7) *Eriovixia excelsa* (Araneidae). (8) *Neoscona theisi theisiella* (Araneidae). (9) *Gasteracantha sanguinolenta* (Araneidae). (10) *Misumenops rubrodecoratus* (Thomisidae). (11) *Hewittia gracilis* (Thomisidae). (12) *Tmarus foliatus* (Thomisidae). (13) *Pseudomicrommata longipes* (Sparassidae). (14) *Thyene natalii* (Salticidae). (15) *Cyrba boveyi* (Salticidae). (16) *Evarcha flagellaris* (Salticidae). (17) *Thanatus dorsilineatus* (Philodromidae). (18) *Uroecobius ecribellatus* (Oecobiidae) Photo credits: Peter Webb.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (KMR), listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON) and country endemism (CEND).

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND	KNOWN SEX
1. Family Agelenidae				
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Mistaria zuluana</i> (Roewer, 1955)	2	LC	STHE	B
2. Family Araneidae				
<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Caerostris sexcupidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Mahembea hewitti</i> (Lessert, 1930)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus</i> Simon, 1897	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona rapta</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Poltys furcifer</i> Simon, 1881	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Singa lawrencei</i> (Lessert, 1930)	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	B
3. Family Barychelidae				
<i>Pisenor arcturus</i> (Tucker, 1917)	2	LC	STHE	F
4. Family Caponiidae				
<i>Caponia spiralifera</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
5. Family Cheiracanthiidae				
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cheiracanthium vansoni</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	B
6. Family Clubionidae				
<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE	B
7. Family Corinnidae				
<i>Apochinomma formicaeforme</i> Pavesi, 1881	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cambalida dippenarae</i> Haddad, 2012	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Corinnomma semiglaurum</i> (Simon, 1896)	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND	KNOWN SEX
8. Family Cyrtaucheniidae				
<i>Ancylotrypa brevipalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Ancylotrypa nuda</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE	B
9. Family Deinopidae				
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	B
10. Family Dictynidae				
<i>Archaeodictyna</i> sp.		NE		
11. Family Entypesidae				
<i>Hermacha mazoena</i> Hewitt, 1915	2	LC	STHE	F
12. Family Eresidae				
<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Stegodyphus africanus</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE	B
13. Family Gallieniellidae				
<i>Drassodella flava</i> Mbo & Haddad, 2019	3	LC	SAE	B
14. Family Gnaphosidae				
<i>Ammoxenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Camillina maun</i> Platnick & Murphy, 1987	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Drassodes solitarius</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Megamyrmaekion transvaalense</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Setaphis browni</i> (Tucker, 1923)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Urozelotes rusticus</i> (L. Koch, 1872)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE	B
15. Family Hersiliidae				
<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE	B *
<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE	B
16. Family Idiopidae				
<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Galeosoma planiscutatum</i> Hewitt, 1919	3	LC	SAE	F
17. Family Linyphiidae				
<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Tybaertiella krugeri</i> (Simon, 1894)	1	LC	AE	B

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18. Family Lycosidae				
<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Foveosa adunca</i> Russell-Smith, Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE	B
19. Family Migidae				
<i>Moggridgea paucispina</i> Hewitt, 1916	3	LC	SAE	F
20. Family Oecobiidae				
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C	B
<i>Paroecobius nicolaii</i> Wunderlich, 1995	4	DD	SAE	B
<i>Uroecobius ecribellatus</i> Kullmann & Zimmermann, 1976	3	LC	SAE	B
21. Family Oonopidae				
<i>Dysderina speculifera</i> Simon, 1907	2	LC	STHE	B
22. Family Oxyopidae				
<i>Hamataliwa rostrifrons</i> (Lawrence, 1928)	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE	B
23. Family Palpimanidae				
<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	F
24. Family Philodromidae				
<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Thanatus dorsilineatus</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C	B
<i>Tibellus gerhardi</i> Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
25. Family Pholcidae				
<i>Quamtana hectori</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Hubert, 2012	3	LC	SAE	B
26. Family Phyxelididae				
<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE	B
27. Family Pisauridae				
<i>Afropisaura rothiformis</i> (Strand, 1908)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Euprosthenops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Nilus rossi</i> Pocock, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B

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28. Family Prodidomidae				
<i>Theuma elucubata</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Theuma purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Theuma schultzei</i> Purcell, 1908	4	LC	SAE	F
29. Family Salticidae				
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Cyrba boveyi</i> Lessert, 1933	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Festucula leroyae</i> Azarkina & Foord, 2014	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Harmochirus luculentus</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Heliophanus charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	STHE	B
<i>Heliophanus orchestra</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Heliophanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1901	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Hyllus argyrotoxus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Mexcala elegans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Myrmarachne inflatipalpis</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE	M
<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Planamarengo bimaculata</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Pseudicius gracilis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Rhene konradi</i> Wesolowska, 2009	4	LC	SAE	B
<i>Stenaelurillus guttiger</i> (Simon, 1901)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
30. Family Selenopidae				
<i>Anyphops bechuanicus</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Anyphops tuckeri</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	F
31. Family Sicariidae				
<i>Hexophthalma hahni</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE	B
32. Family Sparassidae				
<i>Eusparassus jaegeri</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE	B

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<i>Pseudomicrommata longipes</i> (Bösenberg & Lenz, 1895)	1	LC	AE	B
33. Family Tetragnathidae				
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Leucauge kibonotensis</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C	B
<i>Tetragnatha demissa</i> L. Koch, 1872	0	LC	C	B
34. Family Theraphosidae				
<i>Augacephalus junodi</i> (Simon, 1904)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Brachionopus pretoriae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	DDT	SAE	F
<i>Ceratogyrus darlingi</i> Pocock, 1897	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Harpactirella overdijki</i> Gallon, 2010	3	DD	SAE	B
35. Family Theridiidae				
<i>Anelosimus nelsoni</i> Agnarsson, 2006	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Chorizopella tragardhi</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE	F
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE	J
<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C	B
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C	B
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
36. Family Thomisidae				
<i>Ansiae tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Camaricus nigrotesselatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Heriaeus copricola</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Heriaeus crassispinus</i> Lawrence, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Hewittia gracilis</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE	F
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> Lucas, 1864	0	LC	C	B
<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Monaeses quadrituberculatus</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Mystaria savannensis</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Pherecydes lucinae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Runcinia depressa</i> Simon, 1906	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	0	LC	C	B
<i>Stiphropus bisigillatus</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE	M
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	M

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<i>Thomisops melanopes</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C	B
<i>Thomisus congoensis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Xysticus fagei</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Xysticus mulleri</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Xysticus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE	B
37. Family Trachelidae				
<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Fuchibotulus kigelia</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	2	LC	STHE	B
38. Family Trochanteriidae				
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
39. Family Uloboridae				
<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE	F
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C	B
40. Family Zodariidae				
<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	1	LC	AE	B
<i>Diores femoralis</i> Jocqué, 1990	3	LC	SAE	B
<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Diores recurvatus</i> Jocqué, 1990	2	LC	STHE	B
<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	B